

MA-ergic effect of sensory stimulation on the formation of interrelations in visual structures

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The presented work is devoted to a comparative analysis of the influence of monoaminoergic systems (noradrenergic, serotonergic) on the formation of interactions between the structures of the visual analyzer (superior colliculus, lateral geniculate body, visual cortex) against the background of sensory stimulation. Rabbits were used as objects of experimental studies. During the recording of electrical activity in the structures of the vision analyzer, electrophysiological research methods were used, the analysis of the obtained results was carried out by means of a computer software package. From the analysis of the obtained materials of electrophysiological research, it became clear that during sensory stimulation, the active involvement of visual structures in the processing of visual information is clearly manifested, as a result of which a specific resonance effect (mastery of the rhythm) occurs according to the frequency of sensory stimulation. The maximum frequencies of the spectral character of neuromodulatory centers are located in the theta wave range, which corresponds to the frequency of sensory stimulation. Also, rhythmic sensory stimulation leads to an increase in coherent connections between structures. The MA-ergic effect of potential synchronization on the electroretinogram is ambiguous. While electrical stimulation of nR neurons increases the effects of sensory activation, stimulation of LC produces the opposite effect.

Keywords: *electroencephalogram (EEG), nucleus raphe, serotonin, locus coeruleus, noradrenaline, coherence, spectrum, photostimulation*

INTRODUCTION

Knowledge about the mechanisms of plasticity of nervous systems is based on the modern concept of neurorehabilitation (Bogolepova, 2010). Neuroplasticity is the ability of the nervous system to adapt through optimal structural and functional reorganization in response to endogenous and exogenous stimuli (Gusev et al., 2014). This feature ensures the adaptation of the organism and its effective functioning in the changing external and internal environment. The plasticity of the nervous system contributes to the consolidation of memory changes necessary for the restoration of functions after damage to the central nervous system (Yakhno et al., 2012). As it is known, non-specific systems are described in sufficient detail in the literature, possessing pronounced neuromodular effects in the regulation of various functional activities of the brain. In particular, 5-HT-ergic fibers nR were found at the level of the visual system of the brain, containing various 5-HT-receptors, among which the most common are 5-HT_{1B}-receptors (Lee et al., 2008). In the literature, there is information about

the projection of nR on the lateral geniculate body (LGB), and the dorsal parts of the LGB receive visual inputs from the retina, as well as opposite fibers from the visual cortex (Blasiak et al., 2009). The presence of 5-HT-ergic projections in the brain was also observed at different levels of the auditory and taste sensory systems of the brain (Horvath et al., 2003). Some authors note that LC has a pronounced modulating effect on the neurons of the lateral geniculate body (Kratin et al., 1987). Also, the terminations of LC neurons are found in all areas of the cortex, including the primary visual cortex, the primary auditory cortex and the taste cortex, but LC axons are unevenly distributed in these parts of the cerebral cortex. In general, the system of efferent pathways of LC is considered to be quite branched and complex, as in the case of the efferent organization of nR neurons (Belova et al., 1980). Of particular interest is the close morphological connection between LC and nR, as well as biochemical data confirming the inhibitory control of 5-HT-ergic neurons over NA-ergic neurons and vice versa. It is assumed that the function of the NA-ergic system, which originates

from LC-neurons, depends on the interaction of the latter with 5-HT-ergic nR-neurons. In modern literature, there is still no single scientific idea about what system to refer to nR and LC. According to some authors, these derivatives should be considered as components of non-specific ascending activating systems of the brain (Kratin et al., 1987). At the same time, there are widespread opinions about the high degree of functionality, as well as topographical and morphological specificity of MA-ergic systems (Salgado et al., 2011). On the other hand, taking into account the broad understanding of these systems of sensory neurons (Liddell et al., 2012), and also received information about the reconstruction of coherent connections and spectral properties in these cores, the following questions arise about the mechanisms modulating influence of nR and LC on EEG activity of the structure of the visual analyzer allows you, to put forward a scientific hypothesis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research was carried out on adult male rabbits (weight 2.5-3 kg), which were kept in standard vivarium conditions at all stages of the experiment. Experiments were carried out chronically. Nichrome electrodes with a diameter of 0.5 mm were placed in the cortical structures, and nichrome electrodes with a diameter of 0.1-0.15 mm in the subcortical structures were placed for recording EEG potentials. Scalping and implantation of macroelectrodes were performed under Nembutal anesthesia (35 mg/kg) and local anesthesia (0.5% novocaine solution) along the coordinates of the stereotactic atlas were used to register biopotentials. Potentials of the visual cortex (VC), superior colliculus (SC), lateral geniculate body (LGB), nucleus raphes dorsalis (nR), locus coeruleus (LC) were registered. The indifferent electrode was placed in the bone above the frontal sinus. For registration and processing of experimental data, we used a computer-controlled software-hardware complex with a light-emitting diode photostimulator and a set of application programs connected to a personal computer. Parameters of rhythmic photostimulation: intensity 1.4C, frequency 5 Hz, spark duration 150 ms. Analyses of EEG have been conducted using the software "Brainsys" (Russia) in the frequency diapason 0.5-45.0 Hz. The coherent (coh) coefficients for the standard EEG diapasons (delta, theta, alfa, beta1, and beta2) were calculated. Statistical processing of the received data, including the construction of graphs and analytical evaluation

of the spectral and coherent characteristics of the EEG, the significance of intergroup and intragroup differences was assessed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). For bipolar electrical stimulation of the neuromodulatory centers (nR, LC), a laboratory electrical stimulator ESL-2 and the following stimulation parameters were used: amplitude 3.0–5.0 V, frequency 150–200 Hz and the duration of a single impulse is 0.4 ms, the duration of one session of electrical stimulation is 4-5 minutes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the spectral and coherent analysis revealed the ambiguous role of 5-HT- and NA-ergic centers in the regulation of these processes. It has been established that, in contrast to LC, under the influence of electrostimulation of the neurons of the nucleus raphe enhanced generalization of synchronization of the sum of the potentials in the central structures of the visual analyzer. At the same time, it should be noted that for a better understanding of the nature of the participation of various components of the MA-ergic neuromodulatory system in the neurophysiological mechanisms of spatial synchronization of EEG potentials, it is not enough to study only this problem at the level of the background activity of the brain. Therefore, in further study of the existing problem, in addition to studying the characteristics of the production and formation of trace processes formed in the vision analyzer structures in response to sensory stimulation, we conducted a comparative analysis of the role of the MA-ergic neuromodulatory system in these processes. In this regard, of undoubted interest is the analysis of the influence of neuromodulating centers on similar processes under conditions of rhythmic sensory stimulation of the visual analyzer. First, we considered the effect of sensory stimulation on the spectral characteristics of EEG potentials. We tried to show the most typical effects of rhythmic photostimulation (PS) on the EEG spectral characteristics of the studied structures (Figure 1). The known effect of rhythm appropriation during sensory stimulation is clearly seen from the spectrograms in all the studied structures. So, if the background activity of VC is characterized by the predominance of the amplitude-spectral character at frequencies of 3-5 Hz and 4-6 Hz, at the stage after PS exposure, the maximum level of the spectrum shifts to the region of sensory stimulation frequencies and remains in this region. A similar situation is also observed in SC. That is, under the

influence of sensory stimulation, the initial bimodal spectrum power distribution pattern at frequencies of 3–4 Hz and 7–8 Hz is transformed into a unimodal pattern with maximum spectral power in the 4–5 Hz range. In contrast, in the current experimental situation, the formation of a bimodal EEG spectrum power distribution pattern under the influence of rhythmic sensory stimulation at frequencies of 4-5 Hz and 9-10 Hz in LGB is more characteristic (Figure 1C). In the later stages of our experiments, it was studied also the influence of rhythmic photostimulation on the spectral composition of EEG-potentials of neuromodulatory centers nR and LC of the brain. Based on the figure observed at that time, it was known that the formation of the maximum amplitude spectrum of LC and nR EEG potentials occurs in accordance with the frequency of retinal photostimulation (Figure 1, nR (D) and LC (E)). The results of the conducted experiments unequivocally show the active involvement of the studied structures in the processing of visual information, as a result of this, a specific resonance effect (acquisition of rhythm) occurs according to the frequency of sensory

stimulation. The maximum frequencies of the spectral nature of neuromodulating centers are located in the range of theta waves, which corresponds to the frequency of sensory stimulation. Although the spectral nature of delta frequencies is negligible, precisely in this frequency range higher levels of coherent connections were found (Figure 1, D and E).

A similar restructuring of the EEG spectral characteristics is also observed in the potentials of the neuromodulatory centers of the brain. Based on the foregoing, it can be assumed that changes in the spectral characteristics of the EEG can be reflected in the level of coherent connections between the studied structures. The experimental facts listed below also unequivocally confirm this hypothesis. So, it is clear from the shown histogram that after the effect of rhythmic sensory stimulation among the potentials of all studied structures of the analyzer, the average coherent coefficients increase significantly (Figure 2B). Interestingly, the increase in the average coherent coefficients is more typical for the theta range of EEG.

Fig. 1. Effects of rhythmic photostimulation on the spectral composition of EEG potentials in the central structures of the visual analyzer (A, B, C) and neuromodulatory centers (D, E).

Fig. 2. Distribution of average Coh values between the structures of the visual analyzer under the influence of sensory stimulation. A - background, B - after the effect of rhythmic photostimulation on the retina.

At this time, the connections between the subcortical structures of the vision analyzer (VC-LGB) become stronger. The fact that there are certain changes in coherent connections between neuromodulatory centers is also of great interest. The maximum frequency of joint activity of this pair is in the EEG delta range and an increase in the average coherent coefficients for this pair of transmitting electrodes is not typical (Figure 2 B). In these studies, the analysis of the effect of MA-ergic neuromodulating centers on trace processes in the visual system of the brain is of particular interest.

Previously, we found that there are fundamental differences in the effects of LC and nR against the background of the action of rhythmic sensory stimulation on the retina. In contrast to the LC, electrical stimulation of the nR increases the spatial synchronization of the EEG potentials in the central structures of the visual analyzer. In particular, we would like to note that during the stimulation of nR the increase of coherent coefficients between the studied brain structures demonstrates this fact. In this regard, under the

influence of sensory stimulation in the conditions of the formation of trace processes a natural question arises about the direction of influence of neuromodulatory centers on coherent relations of potentials in the visual system of the brain. For this purpose, in the following experiments, we investigated the characteristics of the effect of electrical stimulation of neuromodulatory centers on trace processes in the visual system and we investigated the reflection of the structures of the visual system of the brain in the spatial organization of EEG potentials. The results of experimental studies carried out in this direction are reflected in the following Figure 3. As can be seen from the given histograms, the effects of PS rhythms correspond to the process of mastering the rhythm of sensory stimulation, which is detailed above. At this time, the maximum values of coherent coefficients observed among all analyzed structures of the visual system of the brain EEG are recorded in the theta wave frequency range.

As a result of the electrical stimulation of nR neurons on this background, activation of 5-HT-ergic neurotransmission almost fundamentally

changes the shape of the distribution of coherent coefficients developed as a result of PS. As a result, the maximum level of coherent coefficients shifts to the delta frequency range of EEG waves, and at the same time, the connections in the field of high-frequency EEG potentials are significantly weakened (Figure 3C). Stimulation of nR under the influence of PS against the background of the activation of trace processes makes it possible to maximally increase the amount of 5-HT in the interstitial fluid in the structures of the vision analyzer. Since it is very interesting to study the effect of monoaminergic systems in a comparative manner at all stages of our experimental studies, at this stage, the effects of LC neurons were also studied. In a similar situation, the effects of electrical stimulation of LC neurons caused slightly different changes (Figure 3 D). As in the previous experiments, in the studies from this series primary stimulation of LC neurons, in our opinion, increased the possibility of maximally increasing the amount of NA in the interstitial fluid in the structures of the visual analyzer against the background of the activation of trace processes as a

result of photostimulation.

The results of the study showed that the increasing of NA-ergic neurotransmission against the background of photostimulation, in the frequency range studied at the stage of background activity, the distribution of the average values of the coefficients of coherent connections between the central structures of the vision analyzer is disrupted. Thus, only when the coherent relationships in the potentials of the studied structures under the influence of photostimulation prevail in the theta frequency range of EEG waves (Figure 3 B), spatial synchronization of EEG potentials is disturbed during activation of LC neurons and as a result all studied frequencies of waves in the range coherent coefficients decrease to a minimum level (Figure 3 D). Thus, the results of the experimental studies conducted in this series clearly demonstrate that the spatial synchronization of the EEG potentials of the visual analyzer structures increases during the formation of trace processes in response to adequate sensory stimulation.

Fig. 3. Rhythmic sensory stimulation of the retina in the background effects of MA-ergic systems on the redistribution of mean values of EEG coherent connections between the structures of the visual system. A- background; B – effects of rhythmic sensory stimulation of the retina; C - electrostimulation of nR on photostimulation effects; D- electrostimulation of LC on photostimulation effects.

This is evidenced, first of all, by the results of spectral analysis of EEG waves with a predominance of sensory signaling rhythms.

Results of coherent analysis synchronization of EEG potentials generated in the visual system in response to adequate sensory stimulation indicate the strengthening of generalization. As shown, it is in the theta range of EEG waves that an increase in joint activity between all central structures of the visual analyzer is observed. In particular, it should be noted that a similar pattern of synchronization was observed both in the spectrograms of brain structures and in neuromodulatory centers. However, the effect of various components of this system on the above-mentioned characteristics of synchronization of EEG potentials is not unambiguous. Thus, in contrast to the effect of LC, the prominent formation of sufficiently well-expressed coherent connections in the visual system under the influence of the 5-HT-ergic system is not at the frequency of sensory stimulation, it occurs in the delta wave frequency range of EEG waves. Interestingly, stimulation of the LC in a similar situation has a diametrically opposite effect. In this case, there is a complete disruption of the spatial synchronization of potentials that develop under the influence of rhythmic sensory stimulation.

CONCLUSION

Observing the effect of mastering rhythms in the spectra of EEG waves of vision analyzer structures under the influence of rhythmic sensory stimulation accompanied by an increase in coherent relations between them. While electrical stimulation of nR neurons increases the effects of sensory activation, stimulation of LC produces the opposite effect.

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Görmə strukturlarında qarşılıqlı əlaqələrin formalaşmasında sensor stimullaşmanın MA-ergik effektləri

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Təqdim edilən iş sensor stimullaşma fonunda görmə analizatoru strukturları (dördtəpəlinin yuxarı qabarıları, bayır dizəbənzər cisim, görmə qabığı) arasında qarşılıqlı əlaqələrin formalaşmasında monoaminoergik sistemlərin (noradrenergik, serotonergik) təsir effektlərinin müqayisəli analizinə həsr olunub. Eksperimental tədqiqatlarda obyekt olaraq dovşanlardan istifadə edilmişdir. Görmə analizatorunun strukturlarında elektrik aktivliyinin qeydi zamanı elektrofizioloji tədqiqat metodlarından istifadə edilib, alınan nəticələrin analizi kompüter proqram paketi vasitəsi ilə aparılıb. Öldə edilən elektrofizioloji tədqiqat materiallarının analizindən məlum oldu ki, sensor stimullaşma görmə strukturlarının vizual informasiyalarının işlənməsinə fəal cəlb olunmasını birmənalı şəkildə göstərir ki, bunun nəticəsində də sensor stimullaşmanın tezliyinə müvafiq olaraq özünəməxsus bir rezonans effekti (ritmin mənimsənilməsi) meydana gəlir. Neyromodulyator mərkəzlərinin spektral xarakterinin maksimal tezlikləri teta dalğa diapazonunda yerləşir ki, bu da sensor stimulyasiya tezliyinə müvafiqdir. Həmçinin ritmik sensor stimullaşma strukturlar arasında koherent əlaqələrin artmasına səbəb olur. Elektroretinoqrammada potensiallarının sinxronlaşmasının MA-ergik təsir effektləri birmənalı xarakter daşımır. nR neyronlarının elektrik stimullaşdırılması sensor aktivləşmənin təsir effektlərinin artırdığı halda, LC-nin stimullaşdırılması əks effekt yaradır.

Açar sözlər: *Elektroensefaloqram (EEQ), nucleus rapher, serotonin, locus coeruleus, noradrenalin, coherent, spectral, fotostimulyasiya*